

CP1: MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091
CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
% identity **64.3**

CP1: MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091
CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
% identity **87.5**

CP8: MtrunA17_Chr1g0155251
CP44: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801
% identity **51.1**

File
 Alio
 ↩

CP8: MtrunA17_Chr1g0155251
 CP44: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801
 Homology region, % identity **83.9**

File
Align
CP10: MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101
CP75: MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381
% identity **58.9**

1. CP10 plus 2
2. CP75 minus 1

File
Align
CP20: MtrunA17_Chr1g0190571
CP25: MtrunA17_Chr1g0202001
% identity **58.9**

1. CP20 plus 2
2. CP25 minus 1

Vertical toolbar with icons for home, refresh, zoom, and other navigation functions.

CP23_24: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071
CP101: MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091
% identity **73.5**

Consensus
Identity
1. CP23 plus 2 and CP24 minus 2
2. CP101 minus 2

File
Align
CP33: MtrunA17_Chr2g0283311
CP50: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671
% identity **56.5**

1. CP33 minus 2
2. CP50 minus 2

File
Align
CP37: MtrunA17_Chr2g0299561
CP53: MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171
% identity **53.8**

File
 Alio
 ↩

CP37: MtrunA17_Chr2g0299561
 CP53: MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171
 Homology region, % identity **83.6**

iting Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

✉ 📄

File
Align
CP37: MtrunA17_Chr2g0299561
CP66: MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650
% identity **63.3**

CP51: MtrunA17_Chr3g0096421
CP121: MtrunA17_Chr7g0270811
% identity **72.8**

File
Align
CP53: MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171
CP66: MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650
% identity **93.0**

Vertical toolbar with icons for home, refresh, zoom, and other navigation functions.

File
Align
CP60: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761
CP62: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901
% identity **52.1**

File
 Alio
 ↩

CP60: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761
 CP62: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901
 Homology region, % identity **79.2**

Editing Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

✉ 📄

Home
 Desktop
 Applications
 Recent
 Refresh
 Settings
 %
 Settings
 Back

File
Align
←
CP66: MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650
CP107: MtrunA17_Chr6g0479001
% identity **59.9**

1. CP66 minus 2
2. CP107 plus 2

File
Align
CP72: MtrunA17_Chr4g0023791
CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
% identity **58.8**

File
 Alio
 ↩

CP72: MtrunA17_Chr4g0023791
 CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
 Zoom-in view

🏠
 📄
 📊
 ➡
 🗑
 🔄
 ⚙
 %
 ⚙
 ⬅

CP72: MtrunA17_Chr4g0023791
CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
% identity **56.3**

File
Align
CP85: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415031
CP132: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368731
% identity **74.8**

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
Geneious alignment, % identity **63.1**

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
MUSCLE alignment, , % identity **25.9**

Consensus
Identity

1. CP87 minus 1
2. CP88 and CP89 minus 1

Vertical toolbar with icons for home, refresh, zoom, and other navigation functions.

File
Align
CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
% identity **52.4**

1. CP87 minus 1
2. CP114 plus 2

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
Homology region 1, % identity **87.0**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP87 minus 1 extraction 1
- 2. CP114 plus 2 extraction 1

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
Homology region 2, % identity **77.8**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP87 minus 1 extraction 2
- 2. CP114 plus 2 extraction 2

File
Align
CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
% identity **52.3**

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761

CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331

Homology region 1, % identity **87.0**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP87 minus 1 extraction 1
- 2. CP141 minus 1 extraction 1

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
Homology region 2, % identity **77.4**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP87 minus 1 extraction 2
- 2. CP141 minus 1 extraction 2

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291

CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401

% identity **51.4**

Consensus Identity

1. CP88 and 89 minus 1
2. CP114 plus 2

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401

Zoom-in view, left side

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
Zoom-in view, right side

1. CP88 and 89 minus 1
2. CP114 plus 2

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
Homology region 1, % identity **87.0**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP88 and 89 minus 1 extraction 1
- 2. CP114 plus 2 extraction 1

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
Homology region 2, % identity **80.3**

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
Homology region 3, % identity **77.8**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP88 and 89 minus 1 extraction 3
- 2. CP114 plus 2 extraction 3

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
Homology region 4, % identity **80.3**

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
% identity **49.8**

Consensus Identity

1. CP88 and 89 minus 1
2. CP141 minus 1

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
Zoom-in view, left side

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
Zoom-in view, right side

1. CP88 and 89 minus 1
2. CP141 minus 1

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291

CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331

Homology region 1, % identity **87.0**Consensus
Identity

1 10 20 30 40 45
GAGGAAAAGAAA S Y A A M A R S I G A T T C C C K T A G T A R C G G C G A G C G A A

1 Homology with the transcript of CP141

- 1. CP88 and 89 minus 1 extraction 1
- 2. CP141 minus 1 extraction 1

GAGGAAAAGAAA C T A A C A A G G A T T C C C T T A G T A A C G G C G A G C G A A
GAGGAAAAGAAA G C A A A A G C G A T T C C C G T A G T A G C G G C G A G C G A A

1 Homology with the transcript of CP88_89

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
Homology region 2, % identity **82.0**

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
Homology region 3, % identity **77.4**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP88 and 89 minus 1 extraction 3
- 2. CP141 minus 1 extraction 3

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
Homology region 4, % identity **82.0**

Consensus
Identity

↳ FWD 1. CP88 and 89 minus 1 extraction 4
↳ REV 2. CP141 minus 1 extraction 4

File

Align

←

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291

CP142: MtrunA17_CPg0492381

% identity **50.5**

Annotate & Predict ← Primer Design Save

✉ 📄

Consensus Identity

- 1. CP88 and 89 minus 1
- 2. CP142 plus 1

File
Align
←

CP88_89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291
CP142: MtrunA17_CPg0492381
Homology region, % identity **78.3**

Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

✉ 📄

🏠
📄
📊
➡
🔍
🔄
⚙️
%
⚙️
←

Consensus
Identity

▶ FWD 1. CP88 and 89 minus 1 extraction
▶ REV 2. CP142 plus 1 extraction

CP93: MtrunA17_Chr5g0435191
CP122: MtrunA17_Chr7g1034306
% identity **52.1**

File
Align
←

CP93: MtrunA17_Chr5g0435191
 CP122: MtrunA17_Chr7g1034306
 Homology region, % identity **83.5**

Consensus
Identity

- 1. CP93 minus 1 extraction
- 2. CP122 minus 2 extraction

Home
 Desktop
 Applications
 Recent
 Refresh
 Settings
 %
 Settings
 Back

File
Align
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
% identity **99.8**

Aligning Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

✉ 📄

A vertical toolbar on the right side of the window. It contains several icons: a home icon, a monitor icon, a bar chart icon, a yellow arrow icon, a magnifying glass icon, a refresh icon, a gear icon, a percentage icon, and a left arrow icon.

File
Align
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
Zoom-in view, middle

CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401

CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501

Geneious alignment, % identity **NA**

File
Align
CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501
MUSCLE alignment, % identity **37.1**

CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401
CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501
Homology region, % identity **90.9**

Consensus
Identity

1 10 20 30 40 44
G T G A T C C G A C G G T G C C G A G T T G A A G G G C Y S T C G C Y C A A C G G A T A

Homology with the transcript of CP154

1. CP114 plus 2 extraction
2. CP154 minus 2 extraction

G T G A T C C G A C G G T G C C G A G T T G A A G G G C Y S T C G C Y C A A C G G A T A
G T G A T C C G A C G G T G C C G A G T T G A A G G G C T C T C G C C A A C G G A T A

Homology with the transcript of CP114

Home
Print
Bar chart
Right arrow
Home
Refresh
Settings
Percentage
Settings
Left arrow

File
Seq
CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501
Overview

new Info
Editing Annotate & Predict Primer Design Save

CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501
Geneious alignment, % identity **50.0**

CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501
MUSCLE alignment, % identity **39.0**

File Alio
 CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331
 CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501
 Homology region, % identity **90.9**

CP145: MtrunA17_CPg0492941
CP148_149: MtrunA17_MTg0490471
% identity **60.4**

1. CP145 minus 1

2. CP148 and 149 plus 1

File
Align
CP150_151: MtrunA17_MTg0490971
CP152: MtrunA17_MTg0491151
Geneious alignment, % identity **NA**

Annotate & Predict ⇄ Primer Design Save

✉ 📄

Consensus
Identity

1. CP150 and 151 plus 1
2. CP152 plus 2

CP150_151: MtrunA17_MTg0490971
CP152: MtrunA17_MTg0491151
MUSCLE alignment, % identity **40.5**

Consensus Identity
1. CP150 and 151 plus 1
2. CP152 plus 2

Home
Zoom
Pan
Refresh
Settings
Percentage
Help

CP150_151: MtrunA17_MTg0490971
CP152: MtrunA17_MTg0491151
Homology region, % identity **100.0**

Supplementary Dataset S14. A graphical summary on nucleotide alignments among all 34 primary-source transcripts that have the global or the local similarity to each other. We discriminate between the alignments that concern the entire length of at least one transcript and those that concern only a part of the sequence. We refer to the latter ones as homology regions. They are highlighted with cyan in this dataset and with dark green in cells of Supplementary Dataset 15B. For alignments of the entire sequences, percent identity values are based on Geneious® alignments (Geneious® v. 7.1, Dotmatics Ltd., MA, USA, <https://www.geneious.com>). For alignments of the homology regions, percent identity values are based on BLASTN results (the *Medicago truncatula* genome browser v. 5.1.9). Reference ORFs (refORFs) are shown in yellow. Alternative ORFs (altORFs) are shown in pink. Numbers 1 and 2 on altORFs indicate the following. An altORF1 in this study is defined as the one that starts earlier than an altORF2. Switches from altORF2 to altORF1 are also found in this dataset but are five times less frequent (e.g. CP108 and four other CPs). Positions and the direction of programmed ribosomal frameshifting (PRF) events are labeled with deep purple arrowheads. Blue stars mark alignments with features of special interest. Screenshots are from Geneious® v. 7.1.